

CSR Practices, Identification and Corporate Reputation

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Abstract

Purpose

This study verifies the influence of the dimensions of corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices and consumer involvement on the identification of the individual with the company and the corporate reputation, moderated by the product category

Methodology

A covariance-based structural equation modelling is used to test the model, using a sample of 568 Argentine consumers. A multigroup analysis is employed to assess the moderating effect of the product category.

Findings

CSR practices have heterogeneous influence based on their dimension, and this influence is moderated by the product category. Accordingly, environmental practices promote consumer identification with the company, whereas those economically oriented have a direct influence on reputation. In contrast, social practices contribute to reputation if they are connected to the business model.

Research limitations

The study is focused on Argentina, analysing two product categories (laptops and financial services for final consumers) and using a large, but not strictly random, sample. In order to mainstream the results, it would be relevant to replicate the proposed model in other countries and with other product categories.

Originality

It provides information about the perception of consumers regarding the CSR practices from a multi-dimensional perspective, since they have an uneven effect on identification of consumer with the company and corporate reputation due to the moderating effect of the product category. The findings of this study may be relevant for managers of technology and banking service companies.

Resumen

Propósito

El presente estudio comprueba la influencia de las dimensiones de las prácticas de responsabilidad social empresarial y de la implicación del consumidor sobre la identificación del individuo con la empresa y sobre la reputación empresarial, moderadas por la categoría de producto.

Metodología

Se aplican ecuaciones estructurales basadas en covarianzas para contrastar el modelo, empleando una muestra de 568 consumidores argentinos. Se efectúa un análisis multigrupo para analizar el efecto moderador de la categoría de producto.

Hallazgos

Las prácticas de RSE tienen influencia heterogénea según su dimensión, moderada la influencia por la categoría de producto. Así, las prácticas ambientales promueven la identificación del consumidor con la empresa mientras que aquellas con orientación económica influyen directamente sobre la reputación. Por el contrario, las prácticas sociales contribuyen a la reputación si están vinculadas al modelo de negocio.

Limitaciones de la investigación

El estudio se ha focalizado en Argentina, analizando dos categorías de producto (computadoras portátiles y servicios financieros para consumidor final) y usando una muestra elevada pero no estrictamente aleatoria. Para generalizar los resultados sería relevante replicar el modelo planteado en otros países y otras categorías de producto.

Originalidad

Proporciona información sobre la percepción de los consumidores respecto de las prácticas de RSE desde una perspectiva multidimensional, pues éstas tienen efecto dispar sobre la identificación del consumidor con la empresa y la reputación empresarial dado el efecto moderador de la categoría de producto. Los hallazgos de este estudio pueden ser relevantes para gerentes de empresas de tecnología y de servicios bancarios.

Title: CSR Practices, Identification and Corporate Reputation

1. Introduction

Corporate social responsibility practices (CSR) are a topic of great academic tradition (Carroll, 2015) that begins to be very important for all types of companies due to its great impact on reputation (Maden et al., 2012). It has recently been insisted on the necessary institutionalisation of Corporate Social Responsibility (or CSR) reports (Shabana et al., 2016), and the need for a correct preparation of them is becoming clearer (Gómez-Villegas et al., 2012; Ernst and Young, 2018). This necessary communication approach between the company and its stakeholders is supplemented with another approach focused on understanding how CSR impact on the consumer (Tingchi Liu et al., 2014), given their influence on the positioning of the products and the company and, thus, on their reputation (Du et al., 2007; Fernández Sánchez et al., 2015; Fatma et al., 2015). Their importance derives from the CSR communicating their adherence to desired and desirable values promoting the consumer-company identification (CCI) (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2003; Currás, 2012). This identification is favoured by consumer's involvement with the product, which shows the interest that the subject attributes to the company, and similarly it allows the company to stand out on the consumer's mind (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2003).

In Latin America, companies are increasingly communicating and developing CSR, which have led to an improvement in their sustainable development metrics (Córdova et al., 2018). This has implied a greater commitment with society, primarily in the case of financial and technological companies (Sierra García et al., 2014). Specifically, it is noted that financial companies are pioneers in CSR development, since their reputation relies largely on such practices (Fatma et al., 2014). However, for technological companies, CSR influence is limited by the predominance of consumer's expectations about their innovating capacity (Kim, 2011).

It has been proved that consumers' responses to CSR are not homogeneous (Bhattacharya et al., 2009; Rivera et al., 2016), since the different nature of such practices will also have different influences on the consumer, based on the product category consumed (Tian et al., 2011). In that context, literature has frequently resorted to measuring consumer's perceptions on CSR by means of one-dimensional scales, which is not consistent with multiple practices carried out by companies (Pérez and Rodríguez del Bosque, 2013).

Concurrently, it is deemed relevant to study models that go deeper in the understanding of the causal chain by which corporate reputation is build (Money et al., 2017), highlighting the role of consumer perceptions on the companies' responsible behaviour, and on their experiences related to the product. In this regards, Aldás et al. (2013) call for understanding how CSR dimensions affect corporate reputation. Accordingly, our objective is to contrast an explanatory model of corporate reputation that includes CSR dimensions and consumer involvement, considering that their relations are mediated by consumer's identification with the company and moderated by product category. This will allow to obtaining the guidelines needed for organizations to set up their CSR strategy. Additionally, the study is carried out in Latin America (Argentina), and most literature is concentrated in European and North American consumers (Carvalho et al., 2010; Jaen et al., 2018).

In order to reach this objective, this research is structured in four parts. First, we review literature of all theoretical constructs that support the proposed conceptual model and its relations. Subsequently, we describe the method, sample and variables used in this study. Third, we present the findings, reporting the model's degree of fitting and the results of the hypothesis testing. Finally, we present the conclusions and implications, together with limitations and future research areas.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Impact of CSRP on consumer's identification with the company

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) represents an explicit framework to understand the relations between the company and society (Carroll, 2015), being the consumer one of its main receivers and evaluators (Hillenbrand et al. 2013). As this regards, the sustainable development model is adequate to study the perceptions of consumers on CSRP, since it discriminates the concept dimensions (Alvarado et al., 2017). Thus, the sustainable development model conceives CSR as a set of organizational policies and practices that, within a specific context, considers the expectations of its stakeholders for the fulfilment of economic, environmental and social objectives (Aguinis, 2011; Pérez-Batres et al., 2010).

Within that context, CSRP provide information about the company's objectives to consumers, allowing them to compare their own personality with that of each company in particular. This in turn triggers a process of rapprochement (Bigné et al., 2010; Currás et al., 2009) by which the self-concept overlaps with the perception they have about the company (Bhattacharya et al., 2009; Urde, 2003), promoting closeness and attachment cognitions called consumer-company identification (CCI).

Based on the above-mentioned, and because the CSR is conceptualized from the sustainable development model, we disaggregate the relation analysed between the perceptions of CSRP and CCI considering social, environmental and economic dimensions, and we therefore propose the following hypothesis:

H_1 : The perception of the social dimension of CSRP has a direct and positive influence on CCI.

H_2 : The perception of the environmental dimension of CSRP has a direct and positive influence on CCI.

H_3 : The perception of the economic dimension of CSRP has a direct and positive influence on CCI.

2.2 Impact of CSRP on corporate reputation

From the consumer's perspective, corporate reputation is a collective and aggregate judgment on the economic and social performance of a company and it summarises its general appeal (Brown et al., 2006). Reputation develops from a dynamic process that combines historical behaviours, peer influence, and expectations about the future behaviour of the company (Thagian et al., 2015). It is also the result of the satisfaction of expectations related to the products and the responsible behaviour of the company (Money et al., 2017).

Specifically, the CSRP generate signals of the image that the company wishes to transmit to its target audience, being part of the narrative oriented to the consumer (Bhattacharya et al., 2009). The consumer prefers companies that manifest themselves as socially responsible (Fatma et al., 2015), being more loyal to them (Valenzuela et al., 2010). Thus, the company's social, environmental and economic efforts can become differentiating elements of its offer, supporting competitive advantages (Feldman and Reficco, 2015).

Accordingly, and given the direct and positive relation of consumer's perceptions of CSRP with corporate reputation, it seems consistent to maintain that the same will happen with the other dimensions that comprise CSR conceptualised from the sustainable development model. Therefore, we hypothesize that:

H₄: The perception of the social dimension of CSRP has a direct and positive influence on the company's reputation.

H₅: The perception of the environmental dimension of CSRP has a direct and positive influence on the company's reputation.

H₆: The perception of the economic dimension of CSRP has a direct and positive influence on the company's reputation.

2.3 Consumer's involvement with the product

Consumers use products as elements that contribute to their own identity and to position themselves before their reference groups (Berger and Heath, 2007). Thus, based on consumers' needs, values and interests, one product is more relevant than others (Hong, 2015). Accordingly, when a product is of high involvement, the company is highlighted in the consumers' mind (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2003) and it becomes a valid instrument to meet their social identification needs (Ahearne et al., 2005; Lam et al., 2013). Based on these arguments, we propose the following hypothesis:

H₇: The involvement with the product has a direct and positive influence on CCI.

Indeed, high involvement levels increase the cognitive effort in the search for information, in the evaluation of the product (Walsh et al., 2016), and in the analysis of the social environment that surrounds the consumption situation (Dholakia, 2001). In view of this, the relevant products for consumers that fulfil their expectations will positively contribute to corporate reputation. All this allows proposing the following hypothesis:

H₈: Consumer involvement has a direct and positive influence on corporate reputation.

2.4 CCI as corporate reputation antecedent

Corporate reputation is a cumulative judgment different from the organizational image and identity (Brown et al., 2006), considering that image is a construct before reputation (Heinberg et al., 2017). This is consistent with the findings of Ahearne et al. (2005) who confirm that reputation is not an antecedent of CCI, unlike the perceptions that the consumer may have of the images that the company projects by means of their CSRP, which are an antecedent of CCI.

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3 Additionally, it has been confirmed that perceptions on CSR affect the consumer's
4 global evaluation of companies, mediated by CCI (Currás, 2012; Marín and Ruiz, 2007).
5 Thus, CCI is an antecedent cognitive state of corporate reputation, since when consumers
6 share values (Bhattacharya et al., 2009; Urde, 2003) and personality traits with the
7 organization (Lam et al., 2013) their global evaluation of it improves (He and Li, 2011).
8 This allows proposing the following hypothesis:
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11 H_9 : CCI has a direct and positive influence on corporate reputation.

12 13 *2.5 Product category as a moderating variable*

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15 Having favourable attitudes towards the social and ethical behaviour of a company does
16 not necessarily mean that the consumer presents a coherent behaviour with said attitudes
17 (Becker-Olsen et al., 2006; García de los Salmenes et al., 2005). Thereby, we observe a
18 relation between the product category and the effectiveness of CSR to provide
19 information about the company's honesty and reliability (Tian et al., 2011). Indeed, the
20 product category affects the intensity and consistency of CSR when communicating the
21 underlying competencies of the company (Fernández Sánchez et al., 2015), moderating
22 CCI processes (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2003; Bigné et al., 2010; Marín and Ruiz, 2013).
23 Based on these arguments, we propose the following hypothesis:
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26 H_{10a} : The product *category* moderates the effect of the social perception of CSR over
27 CCI.

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29 H_{10b} : The product *category* moderates the effect of the environmental perception of CSR
30 over CCI.

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32 H_{10c} : The product *category* moderates the effect of the economic perception of CSR
33 over CCI.

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35 Literature shows that product category behaves like a moderating perception of CSR
36 and corporate reputation (Rui et al., 2011; Tian et al., 2011). Thus, when consumers
37 consider that CSR are contrary to their expectations, and are not perceived as integrated
38 into the business model, they have a negative impact on corporate reputation (Aldás et
39 al., 2013), and, consequently, they have to be substantiated (Carvalho et al., 2010). Based
40 on these arguments, we propose the following hypothesis:
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43 H_{11a} : The product *category* moderates the effect of the social perception of CSR over
44 corporate reputation.

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46 H_{11b} : The product *category* moderates the effect of the environmental perception of CSR
47 over corporate reputation.

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49 H_{11c} : The product *category* moderates the effect of the economic perception of CSR
50 over corporate reputation.
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3. Method

3.1 Sampling profile

A non-probabilistic sample was used with age, gender and product category quotas. The effective sample totalled 568 people, 49.3% of which were men. By ages, Generation Y (18-35 years old) makes up 61.4% and Generation X (36-50 years old), 38.6%. By education, 2.4% has not completed secondary studies, 7.3% has completed secondary studies, 48.8% is studying at university and 41.5% has completed university studies.

The sample structure is adjusted to the population proportions of the last Argentine census (National Institute of Statistics and Censuses, 2010), but with a bias towards people with a higher education. This bias was accepted because the questionnaire contained items of certain conceptual complexity. The study was focused on generations “X” and “Y”, since the consumption decisions of these cohorts will have an impact over a long time horizon (Eastman and Liu, 2012).

As regards the sample quota according to the product category, it was equally determined between two categories, in order to classify consumers under a dichotomous variable that would allow evaluating its moderating effect on the proposed model. To select the categories, we start from the conceptual work of Nelson (1970), who classified them in “search”, “experience” and “credibility” categories. The “search” category relates to that in which the consumer explores to gain access to information about the quality of the products prior to purchasing. The “experience” category is that where we gather information about the quality of the product through learning coming from its use. Finally, the “credibility” category refers to when the quality cannot be determined even after use, given the information asymmetry between supplier and demander. With this classification, it was possible to observe the relationship between the product category and the corporate enthusiasm for effecting and communicating its CSRP. Thus, the “experience” and “credibility” categories are attractive, since their CSRP are more effective as a strategic communicational resource to differentiate the offer and encourage purchase decisions (Siegel and Vitaliano, 2007; Tian et al., 2011).

In this framework, we contrasted the opinion of clients of laptop companies (experience category) with that of clients of financial services for end consumers (credibility category). This choice is due to the fact that we have checked that companies offering financial services are markedly present in the first places of the corporate reputation ranking (Merco, 2017). In contrast, those companies that manufacture and market laptops are absent from places of any relevance in that ranking (See Appendix I).

In addition, in Latin America, the companies that market said categories are those that guarantee their CSR reports the most, indicating their sensitivity for showing a responsible behaviour (Sierra García et al., 2014). In short, they are two attractive categories for developing CSRP, but very different at their reputational levels.

3.2 Measures

All the scales used have been validated in prior studies, showing adequate reliability and validity levels. We changed the way certain items were phrased in order to adjust them to Argentine Spanish. Concurrently, we homogenized the form of the scales using 7-point Likert-type (1 = "completely disagree"; 7 = "completely agree"; 4 = "neither disagree nor agree").

Perception of CSR: We applied what is proposed by Alvarado et al., (2017) considering CSR dimensions as exogenous constructs independent of one another, consistent with the works of García de los Salmenes (2005), Alvarado and Schlesinger (2008) and Currás et al. (2018). Thus, it is feasible to check the influence of each dimension of CSR on CCI and corporate reputation.

Consumer's involvement with the product: We applied Hong's scale (2015) which is based on the *Personal Involvement Inventory*, (PII) by Zaichkowsky (1994).

Consumer-Company Identification (CCI): We adopted the work written by Pérez and Rodríguez del Bosque (2015), who, in turn, propose an adaptation of Bergami and Bagozzi's (2000) graphical scale to measure the consumer's cognitive identification with the company.

Corporate reputation: We applied the scale proposed by Ponzi et al. (2011), a unidimensional scale with multiple cross-cultural applications, including Argentina.

Appendix II lists the scales and items used.

3.3 Fieldwork

A personal survey through a pen-and-paper questionnaire and specially trained interviewers were used. There were two groups of interviewers. One conducted the survey for the laptop category and the other, for the category of financial services for the individual customer. The survey was conducted in the city of Cordoba (Argentina) in October 2017. It posed one first question: "Please, indicate the name of the [bank/laptop company] you are a client of". If the individual contacted was not a client, the contact ended, even if that individual had an image/idea of CSR. Therefore, only those who were clients completed the whole questionnaire, focusing their answers on the company of the product they consumed. The reason for this filter is that not all the respondents have an advanced knowledge allowing them to differentiate CSR and, consequently, the selected individuals do know the company about which they are answering the questions. In addition, those who do not have a certain degree of knowledge of the company will not provide a distinguishing answer because companies themselves tend not to show significant differences. This is due to mimetic isomorphism (Martínez-Ferrero and García-Sánchez, 2017); by which companies within the same category find themselves obliged to incorporate CSR replicating the benchmarks of the sector, which has also been noted in Latin American companies (Pérez-Batrez et al., 2010).

4. Results

4.1 Measure adaptation

First, we performed a principal component analysis to see if measurement instruments have configural invariance when comparing the results from grouping consumers according to product category. After this analysis, we dismissed items *Impl2* and *Impl5* (referring to emotions and fascination), in line with the proposal by Mittal (1995) for a correct operationalisation of the cognitive involvement of the consumer with the product.

Second, we conducted the two-step procedure used by Anderson and Gerbing (1988) to assess the psychometric properties of the measurement instruments using a confirmatory factor analysis. No reliability problem was thus detected, since all Cronbach's Alphas are greater than the recommended value of 0.7 (Churchill, 1979), composite reliability (CR) rates for all factors are greater than the recommended value of 0.7 (Fornell and Larcker, 1981), and the average variances extracted (AVE) are greater than 0.50 (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Then, in order to guarantee convergent validity, we deleted those items whose factor loadings were less than 0.70 (Bagozzi and Yi, 1988), these being *sCSR4*, *eCSR1*, *CCI3*, *CCI4*, *CCI5* and *Rep3*. This strategy does not cause significant validity decreases, given the low rates of indicator reduction made (Bell and Lumsden, 1980) (see Table 1).

Insert Table 1 here.

Discriminant validity issues were not detected either, since (see Table 2): a) no confidence interval for the correlation estimate between each pair of factors contained the value 1 (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988), and b) the AVE for each factor is always lower than the squared correlation between each pair of factors (Fornell and Larcker, 1981).

Insert Table 2 here.

We applied the robust maximum likelihood (RML) method, which is suitable for solving non-normality issues of the data, since the estimated Mardia's coefficient is 211.43. This method uses, in the model fit, the statistical scaling of Satorra-Bentler χ^2 (S-B χ^2) (Satorra and Bentler, 1994), which is sensitive to the sample size and multivariate normality deviations, and it therefore tends to be significant (Bentler and Bonnett, 1980). Considering that, literature suggests that the statistic is acceptable if the coefficient between S-B χ^2 and the degrees of freedom is lower than 5 (Wheaton et al., 1977), completing the evaluation of the model with other measures of goodness of fit (Hair et al., 2005; Hu and Bentler, 1999), being the fit indicators those reported by the EQS 6.1 software. Based on these arguments, the adjustment of the measurement model is good (see Table 2).

Finally, we verified the hypotheses using a covariance structure model, whose resulting fit is reasonable (see Table 3). For form invariance testing, factor loading and factor variance (in moderation hypotheses) a multi-group analysis is employed following the methodological guidelines indicated by Aldás (2013). For all the analyses described, SPSS 22 and EQS 6.1 software were employed.

Insert Table 3 here.

4.2 Hypothesis testing

We confirmed that the perception of the environmental dimension of CSR has a positive influence on CCI given the load significance, direction and magnitude ($\beta_2=0.264$, $p<0.05$; acceptance of H_2). However, the perception of the economic and social dimensions of CSR does not contribute to that identification, since it is not significant ($\beta_1=0.064$, $p>0.05$; rejection of H_1 and $\beta_3=-0.015$, $p>0.05$; rejection of H_3).

Both, the perception of the social ($\beta_4=0.092$, $p>0.05$; rejection of H_4) and the environmental dimensions ($\beta_5=-0.126$, $p>0.05$; rejection of H_5) of CSR have no influence on corporate reputation, whereas the perception of the economic dimension of CSR does have an influence on corporate reputation ($\beta_6=0.397$, $p<0.01$; acceptance of H_6).

Furthermore, consumer's involvement with the product is an antecedent variable of CCI ($\beta_7=0.230$, $p<0.01$; acceptance of H_7). Additionally, said involvement has an influence on corporate reputation ($\beta_8=0.405$, $p<0.01$; acceptance of H_8) indicating that when the product is important to individuals, their greatest expectations affect their global assessment of the company.

Finally, it was noted that when consumers have a high CCI, they develop a closeness cognition state with the company that has a direct and positive influence on the corporate reputation ($\beta_9=0.190$, $p<0.01$; acceptance of H_9).

4.3 Moderation Analysis

Table 4 shows the multi-group analysis results, including the structural relationship estimation for each group and their measures of goodness of fit that exceed the critical acceptance values except for the Normed Fit Index (NFI), which is an indicator sensitive to small sample sizes (Bearden et al., 1982). It was noted that the model has a good fit. The Lagrange test applied on the difference significance of S-B χ^2 suggests that all the relationships are significantly different among the groups.

Insert Table 4 here.

However, as for the hypotheses H_{10a} (banks $\beta_{10a}=0.125$; $t=0.723$; laptops $\beta_{10a}=-0.130$; $t=0.645$) and H_{10c} (banks $\beta_{10c}=0.013$; $t=0.149$; laptops $\beta_{10c}=-0.012$; $t=0.112$), interactions are not significant at a structural level in each subgroup, which is why such moderation hypotheses are not accepted.

As regards H_{10b} we noted that the influence of the environmental dimension of the CSR on CCI has a greater effect on experience products (laptops: $\beta_{10b}=0.376$; $t=2.039$) than on experience services (banks: $\beta_{10b}=0.269$; $t=1.664$), and we therefore accept said moderation hypothesis.

Hypotheses H_{11a} is accepted, because the social dimension of CSR has a direct and significant influence on bank reputation ($\beta_{11a}=0.340$; $t=3.130$); however, the social dimension has a negative influence on laptop companies' reputation ($\beta_{11a}=-0.193$; $t=1.651$) since they can be perceived as being disconnected from the business model.

As regards H_{11b} , the product category modifies the strength of the structural relationship between the environmental dimension of CSR and corporate reputation, thus becoming a moderating variable. Accordingly, environmental practices have a significant and negative influence on the banks category ($\beta_{11b}=-0.308$; $t=3.002$); whereas in the laptops category they do not represent signals employed by the consumer to assess corporate reputation ($\beta_{11b}=0.052$; $t=0.475$).

Finally, regarding hypothesis H_{11c} , we noted a moderating effect since the influence of economic practices on corporate reputation is greater on durable goods (laptops: $\beta_{11c}=0.450$; $t=5.111$) than on experience services (banks: $\beta_{11c}=0.374$; $t=5.023$). Figure 1 shows a summary of the results.

Insert Figure 1 here

5. Conclusions

Prior works (Bigné et al., 2010; Du et al., 2007; Marín and Ruiz, 2007) confirm that the perception of CSR contributes to CCI in a positive way using unidimensional scales. This has limited the understanding of which the specific CSR contributing to a greater identification are, and in what contexts. Our findings substantiate, after using a multidimensional scale of CSR, that there is no evidence that the economic and social dimensions contribute to a greater CCI (rejection of H_1 and H_3), whereas the environmental dimension does contribute to a greater CCI (acceptance of H_2). Therefore, corporate practices related to recycling, environmental protection, and marketing of environment-friendly products operate as a powerful symbolic material by which individuals improve their self-concept and their social categorization. These findings are consistent with prior studies about Latin American consumers, which reflect that environmental protection is highly regarded (Marquina and Morales, 2012). In addition, they also confirm that environmental practices are important in improving consumer's perception (satisfaction) (Rivera et al., 2016), and thus, that the consumer develops a greater identification with those companies that carry out environment-friendly practices.

Besides, such effects are greater on durable experience products (moderation H_{10b}), and therefore, the environmental behaviours of laptop companies become differentiating attributes that help the organization stand out with greater intensity, facilitating identification processes (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2003; Bigné et al., 2010; Marín and Ruiz, 2013).

Furthermore, the rejection of H_1 and H_3 can be explained as a consequence of possible low perception levels in the quality of the products under study (He and Li, 2013; Tingchi Liu et al., 2014). Concurrently, consumers may not consider themselves to be the recipients of such practices (Pérez and Rodríguez del Bosque, 2015), that is why they do not get cognitively involved in their interpretation and do not use them as resources for their social categorization.

Subsequently, it was confirmed that consumer's involvement with the product is an antecedent of CCI, consistent with the arguments of Ahearne et al., (2005), Currás (2012) and Lam et al., (2013), since products portray personal goals of identity and lifestyle, and thus they become valid objects for their social categorization (acceptance of H_7). Concurrently, it was noted that CCI has a direct and positive influence on corporate reputation (acceptance of H_9), which confirms the identification capacity of promoting cognitive responses in the consumer that benefit the company (Currás, 2012; Du et al., 2007; Lam et al., 2013). Thus, CCI is a quality indicator of the relationship among the

parties that goes beyond satisfaction and trust, since it lays the foundations of long-term relationships through corporate reputation (Bhattacharya et al., 2009). Therefore, it should be noted that the economic dimension of CSR (acceptance of H_6), as well as consumer's involvement with the product (acceptance of H_8) have a direct and positive influence on corporate reputation, which is consistent with prior studies about Latin American consumers, in countries where the economic dimensions are the most influential elements of CSR (Feldman and Reficco, 2015).

Even though there is no evidence that the social and environmental dimensions of CSR contribute positively to corporate reputation (rejection of H_4 and H_5), at a subgroup level the results are different. The separate study of product categories shows that the social dimension of CSR has a positive influence on bank reputation, whereas it has a negative influence on laptop companies (moderation H_{11a}). Concurrently, it is noted that environmental practices have a negative influence on bank reputation, whereas they have no influence on laptop companies (moderation H_{11b}) which may respond to communicational deficiencies in the technology sector (Du et al., 2010).

These results are consistent with the arguments of Riu et al., (2011) and Tian et al., (2011) concluding that the consumer response varies according to product category, being more effective the use of CSR when practices are perceived as integrated into the business model. These findings are consistent with prior studies about Latin American consumers, who will support those companies developing CSR, provided that such practices are perceived as justified (Carvalho et al., 2010).

Indeed, for the banking service consumer, the social dimension of CSR is as important as the economic dimension; thus, socially-oriented CSR are a feasible source for expectations fulfilment and differentiation, in agreement with the arguments of Fatma et al. (2015). Accordingly, it is confirmed that the different nature of CSR has specific influence on the consumer's behaviour, which is why the selection of such practices should be tailor-made for each organization (Rivera et al., 2016).

These findings have three implications for companies. First, although the experience and credibility categories are attractive for CSR development, they must be consistent with the business model of each company so that they can contribute to corporate reputation. Thus, the consumer can consider that the company's responsible behaviour is well founded, legitimate, consistent and authentic (Aldás et al., 2013; Carvalho et al., 2010). Therefore, developing CSR by only replicating the benchmarks of the sector (Martínez-Ferrero and García-Sánchez, 2017) can put corporate reputation at risk if the consumer does not notice their relation with the product consumed.

Second, the economic dimension and the involvement with the product are the most influential elements for the Latin American consumer when assessing corporate reputation. For that reason, the social and environmental dimensions of CSR are secondary, and they will only have positive effects if they are consistent with the company's activity and seem credible to the consumer. In this regards, social practices are a key element in building bank reputation. Third, CSR focused on the environment are signals that bring psychological benefits to the consumer, since the company creates an identification with ecological values in an attempt to build, on these foundations, a long-term relationship (Lam et al., 2013). These practices are significant in computer products, given their impact on the environment.

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3 Finally, this research is subject to a number of limitations. First of all, we have contrasted
4 the model in two product categories and in a specific range of consumers, which may
5 have caused a bias in the results. Additionally, the sample has a high educational level,
6 another logical requirement that is necessary for understanding some conceptually
7 complicated items. Concurrently, since consumer's perceptions of CSR are sensitive to
8 context influence, the findings of this research should be cautiously transferred to
9 communities other than the Argentine. In the future, it would be relevant to replicate the
10 proposed model including affective dimensions of the constructs under study, in order to
11 better understand why social and economic dimensions have not contributed to
12 identification processes, aiming at improving the explanatory power of the model.
13 Besides, it would be relevant to understand how consumers react to CSR communicated
14 through company-controlled channels (e.g., their sustainability reports) and compare
15 them with others communicated through informal means without the company's own
16 mediation.
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Appendix I. MERCO Ranking of the most mentioned companies by category

Category	Company/Brand	% *	MERCO Ranking position**
Financial services (bank accounts and associated services)	Santander Bank	18.47	10
	Galicia Bank	15.68	11
	Bank of Córdoba	14.63	n.a.
	Macro Bank	13.94	99
	Bank of the Argentine Nation	6.97	n.a.
	Orange Card	6.27	19
	Visa	5.57	40
	ICBC	4.53	82
	HSBC	3.14	27
	BBVA	2.44	20
	MasterCard	1.74	65
	Supervielle Bank	1.39	n.a.
	Other companies	5.23	--
Laptops	HP	21.35	n.a.
	Lenovo	14.95	n.a.
	Samsung	13.52	29
	Asus	9.25	n.a.
	Banghó	7.12	n.a.
	Dell	6.41	n.a.
	Apple	4.27	22
	Toshiba	3.56	n.a.
	BGH	2.49	n.a.
	LG	2.49	n.a.
	Compaq	1.78	n.a.
	Sony	1.78	41
Other companies	11.03	--	

Notes * Percentage of consumers who responded about the company of which they were customers, in each product category

** Ranking of the Corporate Reputation Business Monitor (2017). Available in <http://merco.info/ar/ranking-merco-empresas?edicion=2017>

n.a. = not available for not being included in the ranking.

Appendix II. Scales and items used

Construct		Items	Research
Social CSR	sCSR1	<i>In my opinion, regarding society, the company:</i> Trying to sponsor educational programmes.	Alvarado et al., (2017)
	sCSR2	Trying to sponsor public health programmes.	
	sCSR3	Trying to be highly committed to well-defined ethical principles.	
	sCSR4	Trying to sponsor cultural programmes.	
	sCSR5	Trying to make financial donations to social causes.	
	sCSR6	Trying to help to improve quality of life in the local community.	
Environmental CSR	enCSR1	<i>In my opinion, regarding the environment, the company:</i> Trying to sponsor pro-environmental programmes.	
	enCSR2	Trying to allocate resources to offer services compatible with the environment.	
	enCSR3	Trying to carry out programmes to reduce pollution.	
	enCSR4	Trying to protect the environment.	
	enCSR5	Trying to recycle its waste materials properly.	
	enCSR6	Trying to use only the necessary natural resources.	
Economic CSR	eCSR1	<i>In my opinion, regarding the economy, the company:</i> Trying to maximise profits in order to guarantee its continuity.	
	eCSR2	Trying to build solid relations with its customers to assure its long-term economic success.	
	eCSR3	Trying to continuously improve the quality of the services that they offer.	
	eCSR4	Trying to have a competitive pricing policy.	
	eCSR5	Trying to always improve its financial performance.	
	eCSR6	Trying to do its best to be more productive.	
Implication	Impl1	This product is important to me.	Hong (2015)
	Impl2	The thought of this product makes me excited.	
	Impl3	This product is interesting to me.	
	Impl4	This product means a lot to me.	
	Impl5	This product is fascinating to me.	
CCI	CCI1	I strongly identify with the company.	Pérez and Rodríguez del Bosque (2015)
	CCI2	The company fits with my personality	
	CCI3	I feel good being a customer of the company.	
	CCI4	I like saying that I am a customer of my banking company.	
	CCI5	I feel closely linked to the company.	
	CCI6	I have a strong feeling of membership to the company.	
Corporate Reputation	Rep1	Is a company I have a good feeling about	Ponzi et al. (2011)
	Rep2	Is a company that I trust.	
	Rep3	Is a company that I admire and respect.	
	Rep4	Has a good overall reputation.	

TABLE 1
Psychometric properties of the measurement model: reliability and convergent validity

Factor	Item	λ (t-value)	Reliability			
			α	CR	AVE	
Social CSR	sCSR1	0.822 (23.378) **	0.880	0.886	0.609	
	sCSR2	0.770 (21.189) **				
	sCSR3	0.741 (18.417) **				
	sCSR5	0.782 (20.970) **				
	sCSR6	0.786 (20.507) **				
	Economic CSR	eCSR2				0.817 (22.587) **
eCSR3	0.856 (23.128) **					
eCSR4	0.766 (18.300) **					
eCSR5	0.719 (15.906) **					
eCSR6	0.794 (18.511) **					
Environmental CSR	enCSR1	0.852 (24.763) **	0.940	0.943	0.734	
	enCSR2	0.864 (26.329) **				
	enCSR3	0.842 (24.889) **				
	enCSR4	0.917 (30.948) **				
	enCSR5	0.848 (23.846) **				
	enCSR6	0.814 (23.806) **				
Implication	Impl1	0.745 (15.141) **	0.825	0.829	0.620	
	Impl3	0.895 (22.664) **				
	Impl4	0.709 (17.710) **				
Consumer-Company Identification	CCI1	0.937 (28.508) **	0.823	0.879	0.711	
	CCI2	0.900 (25.581) **				
	CCI6	0.668 (16.321) **				
Corporate Reputation	Rep1	0.859 (23.461) **	0.866	0.872	0.695	
	Rep2	0.886 (26.685) **				
	Rep4	0.749 (16.785) **				
Robust Adjustment Goodness Measures						
S-B χ^2 (260 df) =710,22 (p=0,000)		NFI	NNFI	CFI	IFI	RMSEA (90% CI)
		0.908	0.930	0.939	0.939	0.058 (0.052 0.063)

Notes: λ = Standardized factor loading, α = Cronbach's α , CR = Composite Reliability, AVE = Average variance extracted, S-B χ^2 = χ^2 Satorra-Bentler, df = degrees of freedom, NFI = Bentler Bonnet Normed Fit Index, NNFI = Bentler Bonnet NonNormed Fit Index, CFI = Comparative Fit Index, IFI = Incremental Fit Index, RMSEA = Root Mean-Square Error of Approximation, CI = Confidence Interval, **=<0.05, CSR = Corporate Social Responsibility Practices.

TABLE 2
Psychometric properties of the measurement model: discriminant validity

Factor	Social CSR	Environmental CSR	Economic CSR	Implication	CCI	Corporate Reputation
Social CSR	0.609	0.728	0.298	0.054	0.112	0.129
Environmental CSR	0.821-0.885	0.734	0.234	0.024	0.120	0.075
Economic CSR	0.474-0.618	0.410-0.558	0.627	0.192	0.062	0.372
Implication	0.137-0.329	0.156-0.360	0.354-0.522	0.620	0.078	0.401
CCI	0.248-0.420	0.263-0.431	0.158-0.338	0.187-0.371	0.711	0.151
Corporate Reputation	0.271-0.447	0.183-0.363	0.544-0.676	0.567-0.699	0.304-0.472	0.709

Notes. Values of the Average Variance Index (AVE) in main diagonal. Lower triangular matrix: 95% confidence intervals for each pair of factors. Upper triangular matrix: correlations between the factors. CSR = Corporate Social Responsibility Practices. CCI = Consumer-Company Identification.

TABLE 3
Structural equation model results

Hypothesis	Structural relationship	Std. coefficient	t-Value	Contrast		
H ₁	Perception of the Social dimension of CSRP → CCI	0.064	0.480 ^{NS}	Not accepted		
H ₂	Perception of the Environmental dimension of CSRP → CCI	0.264	2.171 ^{**}	<i>Accepted</i>		
H ₃	Perception of the Economic dimension of CSRP → CCI	-0.015	-0.231 ^{NS}	Not accepted		
H ₄	Perception of the Social dimension of CSRP → Corporate Reputation	0.092	1.092 ^{NS}	Not accepted		
H ₅	Perception of the Environmental dimension of CSRP → Corporate Reputation	-0.126	-1.669 ^{NS}	Not accepted		
H ₆	Perception of the Economic dimension of CSRP → Corporate Reputation	0.397	7.083 ^{***}	<i>Accepted</i>		
H ₇	Implication with the product → CCI	0.230	4.187 ^{***}	<i>Accepted</i>		
H ₈	Implication with the product → Corporate Reputation	0.405	7.070 ^{***}	<i>Accepted</i>		
H ₉	CCI → Corporate Reputation	0.190	4.355 ^{***}	<i>Accepted</i>		
Robust Adjustment Goodness Measures						
S-B χ^2 (260 df) = 710.35 (p = 0.000)		NFI	NNFI	CFI	IFI	RMSEA (90% CI)
		0.908	0.930	0.939	0.939	0.058 (0.052 0.063)

Notes. * = p < 0.1; ** p < 0.05; *** = p < 0.01, NS = Not Significant, S-B χ^2 = χ^2 Satorra-Bentler, df = degrees of freedom, NFI = Bentler Bonnet Normed Fit Index, NNFI = Bentler Bonnet NonNormed Fit Index, CFI = Comparative Fit Index, IFI = Incremental Fit Index, RMSEA = Root Mean-Square Error of Approximation, CI = Confidence Interval, CSRP = Corporate Social Responsibility Practices, CCI = Consumer-Company Identification.

TABLE 4
Moderating effect of the product category

Hypothesis	Structural Relationship	Multigroup Model*						Lagrange's Test			Contrast
		General Model†		Banks		Laptops		Diff. χ^2 (accumulated)	df	P- Value	
		β	t-value	β	t-value	β	t-value				
H10a	<i>The product category moderates the effect of the perception of the social CSR on the CCI.</i>	0.064	0.480 ^{NS}	0.125	0.723 ^{NS}	-0.130	0.645 ^{NS}	12.418	3	0.006	Not Accepted
H10b	<i>The product category moderates the effect of the perception of the environmental CSR on the CCI.</i>	0.264	2.171**	0.269	1.664*	0.376	2.039**	12.837	6	0.046	Accepted
H10c	<i>The product category moderates the effect of the perception of the economic CSR on the CCI.</i>	-0.015	0.231 ^{NS}	0.013	0.149 ^{NS}	-0.012	0.112 ^{NS}	12.615	4	0.013	Not Accepted
H11a	<i>The product category moderates the effect of the perception of the social CSR on the Corporate Reputation.</i>	0.092	1.092 ^{NS}	0.340	3.130***	-0.193	1.651*	5.374	1	0.02	Accepted
H11b	<i>The product category moderates the effect of the perception of the environmental CSR on the Corporate Reputation.</i>	-0.126	1.669*	-0.308	3.002***	0.052	0.475 ^{NS}	10.808	2	0.004	Accepted
H11c	<i>The product category moderates the effect of the perception of the economic CSR on the Corporate Reputation.</i>	0.397	7.083***	0.374	5.023***	0.450	5.111***	12.767	5	0.046	Accepted

† General Model Settings:

S-B χ^2 (260 df) = 710.35 (p<0.01); NFI = 0.908; NNFI = 0.930; CFI = 0.939; IFI = 0.939; RMSEA = 0.058 (0.052–0.063).

* Multigroup model settings:

S-B χ^2 (526 df) = 1013.14 (p<0.01); NFI = 0.875; NNFI = 0.926; CFI = 0.935; IFI = 0.935; RMSEA = 0.060 (0.054–0.065).

Notes. * = p<0.1; ** p = <0.05; *** = p<0.01, NS = Not Significant, β = Standard Coefficient, S-B χ^2 = χ^2 Satorra-Bentler, df = degrees of freedom, NFI = Bentler Bonnet Normed Fit Index, NNFI = Bentler Bonnet NonNormed Fit Index, CFI = Comparative Fit Index, IFI = Incremental Fit Index, RMSEA = Root Mean-Square Error of Approximation, CSR = Corporate Social Responsibility Practices, CCI = Consumer-Company Identification.

FIGURE 1
Structural Relations Model

Notes. * = $p < 0.1$; ** = $p < 0.05$; *** = $p < 0.01$, NS = Not Significant, β = Standard Coefficient, t = t-value, CSRP = Corporate Social Responsibility Practices.